

Interaction of proline, penicillamine and NTA with transition metal ions : A solution ionophoretic investigation

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Manuscript received 01 July 2009, revised 08 June 2010, accepted 18 August 2010

Abstract : The stability constants of metal-proline/penicillamine binary complexes are found to be $10^{9.98}/10^{10.58}$, $10^{8.78}/10^{9.78}$, $10^{5.98}/10^{9.68}$, $10^{5.68}/10^{9.28}$ and that of metal-proline/penicillamine-NTA mixed complexes have been found to be $10^{6.35}/10^{6.00}$, $10^{6.04}/10^{5.85}$, $10^{5.87}/10^{5.75}$, $10^{5.80}/10^{5.57}$ for Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes respectively at 25 °C, ionic strength (μ) = 0.1 M (HClO₄).

Keywords : NTA, ionophoretic investigation, proline, penicillamine, complex.

Introduction

Proline plays very important role in the synthesis of collagen, the major protein of connective tissue in higher animals. The organic material of cornea of eye is almost pure collagen¹ and the penicillamine's use in recent years as a drug² in treating Wilson's disease (hepatolenticular degradation), as a protective agent against radiation³ and as an antidote in metal ion poisoning^{4,5} warrant the examination of their metal chelate properties. A simple ionophoretic tube⁶ has been designed which after standardization yields remarkable results.

Ionophoresis set-up

Results and discussion

Metal-proline/penicillamine binary system :

Figs. 1 and 2 illustrate the relationship between absorbance differences and the pH and thus give an idea of

Fig. 1. Mobility curve – Metal-proline systems

Fig. 2. Mobility curve – Metal-penicillamine systems

the change of overall mobility of the metal ion with change in hydrogen ion status of the system containing Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and proline/penicillamine. A curve with a number of plateaus indicates the formation of certain complex species. A pH plateau is an indication of constant mobility. The first plateau in each case corresponds to a region of pH where metal ions are uncomplexed. In this low pH region, the protonated form of proline/penicillamine is maximum. Further increase in pH from this region onward which naturally leads to increase in ligating proline/penicillamine anion concentration [L⁻] and brings about a progressive decrease in overall ionic mobility of the metal ion species. This decrease indicates formation of complex of the metal ion with the ligand. A point is reached beyond which mobility of the metal ion remains constant regardless of the increase of pH of reaction mixture. This is the second plateau which corresponds to a pH region in which 1 : 1 complex is predominantly formed. One proline/penicillamine anion combines with each metal ion to form cationic complexes with Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} respectively. Beyond this plateau increase of pH has no effect and mobility remain constant.

The overall mobility *U* is a composite parameter contributed by different ionic species of the metal ion and is given by following equation :

$$U = \frac{u_0 + u_1 K_1 [L] + u_2 K_1 K_2 [L]^2 + \dots}{1 + K_1 [L] + K_1 K_2 [L]^2 + \dots} \quad (1)$$

where *K*'s are the stability constant of complexes and [L] is the concentration of proline/penicillamine ion. *u*'s (*u*₀, *u*₁, *u*₂) are the ionic mobilities of different species of the metal ions which can be accessed from the plateaus of the figure. In the region between first and second plateau the system contains overwhelmingly a mixture of free metal ion and 1 : 1 complex. The existence of 1 : 2 complexes can be excluded and hence the third term in the numerator and the denominator of the above equation can be justifiably neglected. *U* would be equal to (*u*₀ + *u*₁)/2 provided *K*₁[L] = 1.

Accordingly the pH corresponding to the average value of *u*₀ and *u*₁ is found from the figure and with the knowledge of the dissociation constant of proline (p*K*₁ = 10.38 and p*K*₂ = 1.90)¹² and penicillamine (p*K*₁ = 1.90, p*K*₂ = 7.85, p*K*₃ = 10.63)¹² the concentration of proline/penicillamine ion at this pH is calculated. Its reciprocal gives the stability constant *K* of the 1 : 1 complexes. The concentration of chelating proline/penicillamine anion

[L⁻] is determined as :

$$[L^-] = \frac{[L_T]}{1 + k_1/[H] + k_1 k_2/[H]^2 + \dots} \quad (2)$$

where [L_T] is the total concentration of the ligand proline/penicillamine and *k*₁ and *k*₂ are the first and second dissociation constants of the proline/penicillamine.

Metal-proline/penicillamine-NTA mixed system :

Figs. 3 and 4 depicts the observation of studies carried out in M-proline/penicillamine-NTA mixed complexes. These graphs clearly show the formation of two plateaus in each case. The first plateau corresponds to binary M-proline/penicillamine complexes whereas the second plateau corresponds to the formation of a new complex.

Fig. 3. Mobility curve – Metal-proline-NTA systems

Fig. 4. Mobility curve – Metal-penicillamine-NTA systems

This new complex may be mixed complex of the type M-L-NTA or pure M-NTA complex. But with the help of related graphs of M-NTA complexes it was found that the absorbance difference in case of new complex is not identical to M-NTA pure complex. Further this mixed complex has greater mobility than that of binary M-proline/penicillamine complex hence these observations confirm the formation of mixed M-L-NTA complex.

Thus it is inferred that the mobility in the last plateau is due to coordination of the NTA anion to a 1 : 1 metal-proline/penicillamine moiety resulting in the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 mixed metal-proline/penicillamine-NTA complex as,

For M-L-NTA complexes the stability constant K' is calculated by using modified equation,

$$U = \frac{u_0 + u_1 K' [\text{NTA}]}{1 + K' [\text{NTA}]} \quad (4)$$

Here u_0 and u_1 are the mobilities of M-L and M-L-NTA complexes.

From the figures concentration of NTA at which overall mobility is the mean of the mobilities of the two plateaus is determined. The concentration of NTA anion at pH 8.0 for this NTA concentration is calculated. K is obviously equal to $1/[\text{NTA}]$.

The stability constant values for binary (M-proline/penicillamine) complexes are Fe^{III} (9.98/10.58) > Cu^{II} (8.78/9.78) > Ni^{II} (5.98/9.68) > Co^{II} (5.68/9.28) and for (M-proline/penicillamine-NTA) mixed complexes are Fe^{III} (6.35/6.00) > Cu^{II} (6.04/5.85) > Ni^{II} (5.87/5.70) > Co^{II} (5.80/5.57) which follows the Irving-William's¹³ order for the stability constants of transition metals of the first transition series. It is observed from the above studies that the stability constants of M-penicillamine complexes are higher than those for the M-proline complex which infers that bond formation in the M-penicillamine complex is stronger than that in the M-proline complex.

Experimental

Metal-proline/penicillamine binary system :

One set of 15 ml solution each containing 1×10^{-3}

M , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , $0.1 M \text{HClO}_4$ and $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ proline/penicillamine was prepared at different pH values (by adding NaOH solution). In case of Fe^{III} , $1 \times 10^{-4} M \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}$, $0.1 M \text{HClO}_4$ and $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ proline/penicillamine was used. 10 ml of this solution is taken in an electrophoretic tube and then thermostated at 25°C . Two platinum electrodes were dipped in each arm cup and a 50 V potential difference was applied between them. Electrolysis of the solution was done for 45 min, after which the middle stopper of the tube is closed. The solution of the anodic compartment was taken out in a 15 ml flask. The copper content of the solution was converted into copper thiocyanate⁷. The volume was raised to a mark in the flask and the absorbance at 408 nm was measured with CZ-specol spectrophotometer. The Co^{II} content of the anodic compartment was converted into cobalt thiocyanate⁷ complex and absorbance at 625 nm was measured after making up the volume to 15 ml. The Ni^{II} content was converted to nickel dimethylglyoximate⁸ and absorbance was taken at 445 nm. Similarly the Fe^{III} content of the anodic compartment was converted to Fe thiocyanate⁸ complex and absorbance was measured at 480 nm against a reagent blank. These observations are graphically represented in Figs. 1 and 2.

Metal-NTA binary system :

The experiments for binary complexes of the Fe^{III} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Co^{II} -NTA are prerequisite for the study of metal-proline/penicillamine-NTA ternary complexes. These studies have been carried out by Aziz⁹ and Singh¹⁰ and their observations have been taken for comparison with our observations found in case of ternary complexes.

Metal-proline/penicillamine-NTA mixed system :

The studies of mixed complexes were carried out by progressive addition of secondary ligand NTA from $1 \times 10^{-6} M$ to $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ at a fixed pH 8.0 to a mixture of metal ion (having same concentration as in binary systems), $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ proline/penicillamine and $0.1 M$ perchloric acid. The reason behind keeping the reaction mixture at pH 8.0 is that much ahead of this pH the simple binary complexes of metal-proline/penicillamine and M-NTA are formed and remain intact even beyond this pH. The amount of secondary ligand NTA was increased each

time in the ionophoretic tube and the electrolysis of the solution and its observations were recorded each time as it was done in case of binary complexes. These observations are graphically represented in Figs. 3 and 4.

A number of factors¹¹ (e.g. diffusion, ionic strength and temperature) obviously vitiate the ionophoretic mobility of a particular ion. The technique described here is almost free of these vitiating factors and the reliability may vary to $\pm 2\%$. ± 0.1 variation in absorbance values can be easily measured with sensitive instrument.

Conclusion :

In the last, it is concluded that this simple and handy ionophoretic technique can be used as a strong tool for the study of metal-ligand interactions in binary and mixed complexes in solution⁶. Also this technique can be used to reduce the level of these metal ions in living system through complexation in solution. These results may also be used for the resolution of racemic mixtures of penicillamine and other amino acids.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad for providing research facilities. Authors are also thankful to UGC, New Delhi for financial assistance.

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